

SHORT FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION MECHANISM IN SiC/AL 2024 COMPOSITES

Hui Zhao , Changzheng Zhao , Xiaodong Jin
Composites Institution, Shanghai Jiao Tong University
Shanghai 200030 , PRC

ABSTRACT

The propagation curves of Short Fatigue Crack (SFC) were determined in CT specimens of aluminum alloy 2024 and its composites with different volume fraction of silicon carbide particles (SiC_p) which are aged at peak in air, and the effect of particles and precipitates on SFC propagation was examined. It is shown that the growth rates of SFC are higher than that of long fatigue crack on the near-threshold ΔK in four kinds of composites ($V_f=0, 5\%, 10\%, 15\%$) respectively, and the growth rates of SFC decrease first to a minimum and then increase with increasing ΔK . The propagation resistance of SFC in the composites is worse in comparison with Al 2024. The precipitates in matrix of Al 2024 were found in composites, and it is the reason of the decrease of the propagation resistance of SFC in the composites.

INTRODUCTION

Recently, metal matrix composites with ceramic short-fiber whisker or particulate reinforcement have attracted the interest of scientists and engineers because of their generally isotropic physical and mechanical properties. In particular, aluminum alloys reinforced with SiC have been shown to provide improved stiffness, strength, high-temperature properties and wear resistance in comparison with monolithic alloys. These materials are promising for aerospace and automotive applications, where materials that are both stiffer and lighter are major requirement. In addition to their isotropic mechanical properties, SiC-particulate-reinforced aluminum alloys can be fabricated economically by conventional metallurgical and mechanical processes. Such advantages help to compensate for the fact that they provide less efficient reinforcement than short fibers and whiskers.

The fatigue properties of such materials are of very importance among their conventional mechanical properties, especially of short fatigue crack which is becoming increasingly recognized and recent efforts to systematically examine these phenomena have been increasing [1] [2] [3]. Unfortunately, that of MMCs has been treated in only a limited number of papers. In the present study Short Fatigue Crack behavior is examined in SiC-particulate-reinforced aluminum alloy composites with different particles distributions, and the influence of Al matrix on the crack path is discussed.

MATERIALS AND TESTING

The 2024 Al alloy composites reinforced by SiC particles were chosen for study. The composition of 2024 Al alloy is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The composition of 2024 Al alloy [1]

main composite wt%			impurities wt%					
Cu	Mg	Mn	Fe	Si	Zn	Ni	Fe+Ni	Sum
3.8-4.9	1.2-1.8	0.3-0.9	0.5	0.5	0.3	0.1	0.5	1.5

The average particle diameter of SiC is 14 μm .

The procedures of producing composites are as followings:

2024 Al alloy and SiC casting ---- ingot ---- hot-pressing in vaccum at 570°C ---- plate (100×50×5mm) ---- 498 °C solution heat treatment for 20 minutes ---- quenching in water ---- 187°C aging [2].

For comparative analysis , the 2024 Al alloy is also manufactured by the same procedures (the 2024 Al alloy is regarded as a composite with SiC Vol pct = 0 in this paper).

Compact tension specimens (CT) were used with $w = 25.4\text{mm}$, which were machined by linear cutting machine.

The Short Fatigue Crack growth tests were performed with a slow-strain fatigue testing machine. The stress ratio R was 0.2, with a sinusoidal wave formed at 0.5Hz. The Short Fatigue Cracks initiate from the notch of linear cutting under proper load. Crack lenght was monitored through a traveling optical microscope (magnification $\times 30$). After testing the specimens were polished and eroded, then examined under metallurgical microscope. A PHILIPS SEM515 was used to observe the fatigue and fracture surface sputtered with Au.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. MICROSTRUCTURE OF SiC/2024 AL COMPOSITE

Fig.1 shows the microstructure of SiC/2024 Al composites after hot-pressing and peak- aging treatment. No voids or regions of macroscopic particle segregation were found in the composite.

As shown in Fig. 1, the grain size of the composites is smaller than that of Al alloy, and decreases with the increase of SiC Vol pct. This is the result that the SiC particles impede the grain growth.

Fig. 1 also reveals the presence of numerous small particles distributing along the grain boundary and around the particulate SiC. When the Vol pct of SiC increases, the size of the precipitates tends to decrease, and the distribution of them tend to disperse more uniformly. EDX was employed to analysis the composition in these precipitates, which is shown in Table 2. Compared with Table 1, it could be found that, the 2024 Al in the present experiments is rich in Mg, and that

a. Al 2024 b. Al 2024-vol5%SiC c. Al 2024-vol10%SiC
 Fig.1 The Microstructure of Composite Materials

the precipitates are rich in Cu, Fe, and some of Mn. Referred to the EMP microanalysis, these small precipitates are close to the S precipitate ($(FeMnSi)Al_6$).

Table 2. EDX analysis of composition

		Cu	Fe	Mn	Mg	Si
2024 Al alloy	average composition	5.65		0.78	2.72	
2024 Al alloy	precipitates	20.52	14.53	6.53	2.35	
composite of 15Vol pct SiC	precipitates around SiC	7.34	7.11	5.16		60

The S precipitates, especially its distribution along the grain boundary will allow the fatigue crack to propagate along the grain boundary.

2. SHORT FATIGUE CRACK GROWTH RATE TESTS

Fig.2 Short Fatigue Crack growth rate curves

Fig.2 shows the Short Fatigue Crack growth rate curves in the composites after data processing according to ASTM standard. The most significant feature of the test results is that short cracks begin growing rather rapidly below the ΔK_{th} , but may gradually slow down as the ΔK increases,

then the growth rate increases. Similar observations have been reported in alloys. It should also be noted that this feature of 2024 Al is most distinct, while the feature of 15%vol SiC-Al is least distinct, and that the fatigue resistance with increasing Vol pct of SiC in composite.

The literature [5]-[9] suggests, that the accelerated short crack behavior is attributed primarily to restrictions in the development of crack tip shielding (principally from roughness-induced crack closure) with cracks of limited wake. The plastic size of crack tip is calculated by Equ.1as following :

$$r_p = K_I^2 / (2\pi\sigma_s^2)$$

which is approximately 0.02 mm. Considering the initiate crack length in present experiment ($a_0 > 0.02$), the crack size is more than the crack tip plastic-zone, therefore the approach of linear-elastic fracture mechanics (LEFM) analysis is effective. Short cracks, by virtues of their limited wake, are less able to develop the same magnitude of shielding as equivalent long cracks at the same nominal ΔK , and thus experience a larger local “driving force” in causing significantly enhanced short crack growth rates. Yet the crack growth resistance primarily from crack closure. The ΔK_{eff} may reduce due to the counter-balance between the driving force and resistance such that the crack growth rates decrease. With increasing crack size, K_{cI} values gradually approach saturation long crack values, such that the small crack growth rates merge with long crack results.

3. SHORT FATIGUE CRACK PATH PROFILE

a. Al 2024

b. Al 2024-Vol 5%SiC

c. Al 2024-Vol 15% SiC

Figure 3. Optical micrographs of Short Fatigue Crack path

Fig.3 shows the optical micrographs of Short Fatigue Crack path of three composites. From it several typical fatigue crack paths are considered in the composites.

- a) Crack propagates mainly along the precipitates, as shown Fig 3-a, c.
- b) Crack deflects on the precipitates, as shown Fig 3-c therefore results in the zigzag path.

c) Crack propagates along the particle-matrix as shown in Fig.3-b. This is attributed to the precipitates around the particulate SiC, which would weaken the bond strength between the particle and matrix.

A lot of studies [10] have investigated the influence of particles on fatigue crack growth path. Present experiment shows that, besides the influence of particles on the fatigue crack growth path, matrix (including the precipitates) also has great influence on the crack growth. Since a great number of discontinuous precipitates distributing along the grain boundary and the interface, fatigue cracks often intend to propagate along the grain boundary and interface. Therefore, while the influence of particle on the fatigue crack path is being evaluated, the influence of precipitates along the interface and grain boundary should also be given consideration.

4. FRACTOGRAPHY

a. Al 2024

b. Al 2024-Vol 5%SiC

Fig.4 SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of short fatigue crack.

Fracture surfaces at middle- ΔK range were examined by SEM, as shown in Fig.4 . Typical striations are found in Al alloy resulted from complete plastic deformation. In the composites (5, 10, 15 Vol pct SiC), the fatigue surfaces are relatively smooth and of some brittleness. This is due to the resistance of SiC particles against the plastic deformation of matrix alloy. By careful examination, a few secondary cracks could be found, relative to the precipitate in the matrix.

5. THE REASON OF REDUCTION IN SHORT FATIGUE CRACK RESISTANCE OF SiC-Al

Based on the above analysis, it is clear that, by the presence of particles, the precipitates size reduces, and their distribution disperses. Therefore, the opportunity of that crack encounter precipitates and particles will increase, or we could say the number of crack propagation passage way will increase. Hence the crack growth rates in composites will be faster than that in Al alloy.

CONCLUSION

1. The Short Fatigue Crack resistance of composites is less than that of Al alloy. This could be explained by that the number of crack propagation passageway increases due to the presence of particles and precipitates.

2. Similar to metal materials, the near-threshold growth rate of short fatigue crack of composites first decrease to a minimum and then increases with increasing ΔK .

REFERENCES

1. Yu Weicheng, Yuan Jincai, Wang Zhongguang, Fatigue behavior of SiC_p/6061Al composite, *Metal Acta*, Vol 26, B428-432(1990)
2. Liu Bing, *Thesis of Master Degree*, Shanghai Jiao Tong University (1993)
3. Li Qun, *Thesis of Master Degree*, Shanghai Jiao Tong University (1990)
4. *Metallographic photo of deformatiic Al alloy*, 90, Metallurgic Press, (1976)
5. Wang Zhongguang, Zhang Yun, Hu Zhuangqi, Fatigue crack propagation in Al-Li alloy 8090, *Metal Acta*, Vol 28, 230-236 (1992)
6. Venkateswara Rao K. T., Yu W, Ritchie R.O., Fatigue crack propagation in Al-Li alloy 2090: Part II, small crack behavior, *Metellurgical Transactions A*, Vol 19A, 563-569 (1988)
7. Nicholls D. J., Martin J. W. , Small crack growth in the Al-Li alloys 8090 and 8091, *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct*, Vol 13, 83-94 (1990)
8. Miller K. J. , The behavior of short fatigue cracks and their initiation, Part 1-A review of two recent books, *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct*, Vol 10, 75-91 (1987)
9. Guin F. , Stevens R. N. , The nucleation and growth of short fatigue cracks both at plain surfaces and notches, *Fatigue Fract. Eng. Mater. Struct*, Vol 13, 625-635 (1990)
10. S. Kumai, K. Yoshida , Effects of the particle distribution on fatigue crack growth in particulate SiC/6061 Al alloy composites, *Int. J. Fatigue*, 14, 105-112 (1992)